

A Real-World Dataset of Ingredient Images for Food Computing

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Abstract. Computing technologies for food analysis have recently attracted significant attention due to their potential to support applications that promote healthier lifestyles, such as diet monitoring and food recommendation systems. These tools can help reduce the risk of diet-related diseases. A key component in developing such applications is the automatic recognition of food images, which alleviates the need for users to manually log consumed or available ingredients. While numerous datasets exist for prepared food, there are few publicly available resources that focus specifically on food ingredients. In this work, we present a dataset comprising approximately 4,000 densely annotated images of food ingredients and food products, intended to support the development of food-related applications. Each image includes instance segmentation annotations, capturing food items as they might appear on refrigerator shelves or tables, thus providing rich contextual information for recognition tasks. We present a detailed analysis of the dataset’s composition. Then, to assess its quality and utility, we report experimental results using several neural network models for instance segmentation.

Key words: Ingredients dataset, computer vision, instance segmentation

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the field of food computing has gained significant attention, offering essential technologies for both research and practical applications in food and health domains. A central goal in this area is the automated recognition of diverse food types, along with detailed profiling of their nutritional and caloric content. While considerable progress has been made in tasks such as dish classification, recipe generation, and food image retrieval, a critical gap remains in the precise localization and classification of individual food ingredients. This challenge, known as food ingredient segmentation, requires not only the identification of each ingredient category but also its pixel-level localization within the image.

Accurately identifying ingredients is crucial for image-based dietary assessment and personalized recommendation systems. Most publicly available food-related datasets, and the models trained on them, primarily focus on prepared dishes. In contrast, our work addresses this gap by introducing a novel dataset containing densely annotated images of food ingredients, semi-prepared products, and condiments captured in real-world domestic environments, such as refrigerator shelves and kitchen tables. Each image is annotated with instance segmentation masks, allowing for fine-grained delineation of individual ingredients in cluttered and context-rich scenes.

To evaluate the dataset in realistic conditions, we developed a prototype smart fridge application integrating segmentation models trained on our data, as described in [1]. A standard refrigerator was outfitted with off-the-shelf components, including webcams,

weight sensors, lighting, and a Raspberry Pi 4, enabling it to recognize ingredients and monitor their consumption. An ontology-based recommender system generates recipe suggestions based on detected ingredients, which are presented through a user-friendly interface on an attached tablet.

Our dataset enables the training of models that can detect a broader range of classes, including basic ingredients, supporting a more proactive approach to dietary assistance. Instead of simply tracking what has already been consumed, intelligent agents can analyze fridge or pantry images and suggest recipes that align with user preferences and dietary needs. Beyond recommendation systems, ingredient detection can support other applications such as robotic sorting of grocery items or automated inventory monitoring in smart fridges, with integration into retail supply chains.

Compared to most publicly available datasets, our proposed dataset is one of the few designed specifically for supervised instance segmentation of food ingredients. Unlike classification or detection tasks, segmentation provides dense, pixel-level ground truth, which enhances model performance, particularly in cluttered environments like refrigerators or kitchen shelves.

This paper presents the methodology used in our image acquisition process, elaborates on the composition of the dataset, and provides a benchmark evaluation of neural network models trained using the instance segmentation masks. The main contributions of this work can be summarized in two categories:

- *Dataset:* We collected, processed, and annotated a dataset of 3,977 images, called *IntAli*, containing food ingredients and food products placed on refrigerator shelves or tables, using instance segmentation maps. The dataset covers 166 distinct ingredient classes, including an "Others" label, and features a total of 11,904 segmentation instances.
- *Experimental Benchmark:* We conducted a benchmark evaluation by training and testing several deep neural network models for instance segmentation on our dataset. In addition to segmentation, the experiments included object detection tasks using bounding boxes extrapolated from the ground-truth segmentation masks. Since some applications may not require full segmentation, bounding boxes can serve as a sufficient alternative. We provide details on the hyper-parameters used and the data augmentation techniques applied during training.

The structure of the paper is as follows. In Section 2, we review existing datasets and highlight how our dataset differs. Section 3 details the data collection and annotation process. Section 4 presents the experimental setup and discusses the results obtained from benchmarking. Finally, Section 5 offers conclusions and outlines future research directions.

2. Related Work

To our knowledge, there is no publicly available dataset that provides instance-level segmentation masks for raw food items photographed both on refrigerator shelves and in natural domestic settings like tables or pantries. Most existing datasets focus on food detection via bounding boxes or classification, and many rely on synthetic images generated with 3D rendering for domain adaptation studies, with the main point of interest for most being already prepared dishes.

Rajpura et al. [2] used synthetic refrigerator scenes based on over 600 CAD models

from ShapeNet [3] and proved improved transfer learning capabilities when combining real and synthetic data. Gudovskiy et al. [4] introduced the FRIDGR dataset, which includes 80k Blender-generated images designed for visual reasoning tasks. SKU-110K [5] addresses detection in densely packed retail shelves. Although not food-specific, it tackles challenges similar to those in fridges, such as overlap and clutter, using Soft-IoU and Expectation Maximization enhancements. FoodDet [6] proposes a two-stage system designed for detecting multiple, diverse food items within the challenging and cluttered environment of a refrigerator, although the dataset is not publicly released.

Several dish classification-focused datasets exist. ChineseFoodNet [7] focuses on Chinese cuisine, combining web recipe pictures with real dish photos to capture large variations in food presentations. VIREO-172 [8] provides comprehensive food images with detailed ingredient-level annotations covering major food groups including vegetables, meat, seafood etc. ETHZ Food-101 [9] contains manually reviewed test images and intentionally noisy training data designed to simulate real-world classification challenges. UPMC Food-101 [10], while using the same 101 food categories as ETHZ Food-101, differs by providing accompanying textual descriptions, making it a multimodal dataset suitable for both visual and text-based food classification research. The Food-11 [11] dataset organizes images into broad food categories such as bread, dairy products, desserts, and fried foods, providing a more manageable dataset for initial food classification experiments

Few datasets focus on ingredient segmentation. Wu et al. [12] introduced FoodSeg103 and FoodSeg154, containing 103 and 154 classes respectively. However, only FoodSeg103 is publicly available.

Several works addressing the challenges of automated nutrition estimation from food images exist. Qi et al. [13] introduced the FastFood dataset, a comprehensive collection of 84,446 images across 908 fast food categories with detailed ingredient and nutritional annotations. Chen et al. [14] introduced MetaFood3D, a pioneering 3D food dataset designed to bridge the gap between general 3D vision research and food computing tasks by providing comprehensive nutrition annotations alongside rich 3D data modalities.

In contrast, our *IntAli* dataset provides real-world images with dense instance-level segmentation masks across 166 ingredient classes. Like SKU-110K, our crowdsourced approach introduces high variability in lighting, angles, and arrangements. All annotations follow the COCO format, enabling both segmentation and detection tasks. Table 1 provides a comparative summary of existing food-related datasets, highlighting their primary tasks, number of classes, images, and annotated instances, and contrasts them with our proposed dataset.

Table 1. Comparison of existing datasets with our proposed food ingredient dataset.

Dataset	Task	Classes	Images	Instances
<i>ChineseFoodNet</i> [7]	Classification	208	185k	-
<i>VIREO-172</i> [8]	Classification	172	110k	-
<i>ETHZ Food-101</i> [9]	Classification	101	101k	-
<i>UPMC Food-101</i> [10]	Classification	101	100k	-
<i>Food-11</i> [11]	Classification	11	16k	-

<i>FRIDGR</i> [4]	Object Detection	14	80k	Unknown
<i>SKU-110K</i> [5]	Object Detection	110,712	12k	1.7M
<i>FoodDet</i> [6]	Object Detection	80	50k	Unknown
<i>FoodSeg103</i> [12]	Semantic Segmentation	103	7k	42k
<i>FoodSeg154</i> [12]	Semantic Segmentation	154	9.5k	60k
<i>Ours</i>	Instance Segmentation	166	3977	11,904

3. Proposed Dataset

3.1 Dataset Description

During the design of the data collection phase, we first defined the categories of food to be included and identified the specific ingredients for each category. By analyzing a variety of recipes, we determined which ingredients were most commonly used. Based on this analysis, we established the following ten ingredient categories:

- Spices, Flavourings, Sauces & Cooking/Baking Aids – Includes common flavor-enhancing ingredients and items that assist in food preparation, typically contributing to taste and process rather than nutritional value.
- Vegetables – Includes all types of vegetables.
- Fruits – Includes all types of fruits.
- Meat and Seafood – Encompasses various meats, sausages, and seafood.
- Cereal-Based Products – Covers items such as flour, cereals, pasta, and pastries.
- Canned Foods – Includes all types of canned products.
- Sweets – Contains confectionery items such as chocolate, ice cream, and similar desserts.
- Eggs and Dairy – Includes eggs and all dairy-based products.
- Drinks – Covers both alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages.
- Half-Cooked Meals – Consists of frozen or partially prepared foods and instant meal kits.

The construction of the dataset was carried out in two main stages:

1. Image Collection Stage – Images were captured in two types of domestic contexts: with ingredients placed on tables and with ingredients arranged on refrigerator shelves.
2. Image Annotation Stage – A curated selection of the collected images was annotated using instance-level segmentation masks.

3.2 Image Collection

The image collection process spanned two months, during which we assembled a dataset of 4,019 images. Each image was tagged with the contained ingredients, their quantities (including value and unit of measurement), and the image type (e.g., captured from a refrigerator or another setting). Data collection was carried out by both project team members and volunteers, totaling 41 individual contributors.

The process was facilitated by a custom-built software platform designed specifically for the collection phase. This platform allowed users to manage their image galleries by uploading, annotating, and deleting images. Only images in JPG or PNG format were accepted, with supported resolutions ranging from HD (1280×720) up to 8K

(7680×4320).

To ensure diversity in the dataset, we asked each volunteer to upload 100 color images, following a structured distribution:

- 10 images (one per category), each containing a single type of ingredient;
- 10 images (one per category), each containing two different ingredients;
- 30 images containing two ingredients from different categories;
- 50 images containing three or more ingredients from any category.

For these 50 images, we proposed that half be taken with ingredients placed inside the refrigerator, and the other half with ingredients arranged on a table.

Of the 4,019 images collected, 3,313 (82.4%) depicted ingredients on tables or shelves, while 706 (17.6%) were taken from refrigerator shelves. As a final step in the data collection phase, a manual validation process was conducted by the team to assess the quality and relevance of each submission. Based on this review, 42 images were discarded, and the remaining 3,977 images were forwarded to the annotation stage.

3.3 Image Annotation

We carried out the annotation phase using CVAT (Computer Vision Annotation Tool) [15], a free and open-source platform designed for computer vision tasks such as object segmentation and annotation. CVAT supports multiple object types, enables instance-level annotation, offers a user-friendly graphical interface, and supports exporting in various standard formats. These features made it an appropriate choice for our project.

The CVAT server was configured to handle all images collected during the data acquisition phase. In CVAT, annotations are organized into tasks, which can be subdivided into jobs, allowing multiple annotators to work in parallel. To ensure a balanced workload, we implemented an algorithm that selects 50 images per task, aiming to equalize the number of instances needing annotation across tasks. Each task was then divided into five jobs, each containing 10 images. In total, 80 segmentation annotation tasks were generated from the 3,977 collected images.

Ground-truth annotation involved delineating the shape of each ingredient instance and assigning a class label. For this, we used instance segmentation rather than semantic segmentation. Unlike semantic segmentation, which assigns a single label to all objects of the same type, instance segmentation differentiates each object individually, even if they belong to the same class. This method ensures that every distinct ingredient in a crowded scene is annotated separately. The dataset was labeled using the COCO annotation format.

Initially, 414 unique ingredient classes were identified during image collection. However, many of these appeared in too few images to support model training. During annotation, these were either merged into more common classes (e.g., “linguine” merged into “spaghetti”) or grouped under generalized labels (e.g., “Other Pasta” under the cereal-based products category). In total, 11 high-level ingredient categories were defined, including an additional “Others” category, which aggregates rare or unidentifiable ingredients. This category appears in 28 images.

After class reassignment, the final version of the dataset consists of:

- 3,977 annotated images
- 166 ingredient classes (including the “Others” label)

- 11,904 annotated instances

Figure 1 shows the distribution of ingredient classes across the 11 defined categories. Figure 2 illustrates the image-wise distribution of these categories before and after the relabeling process. In this context, each category acts as an accumulator for its associated ingredient classes: if an image contains multiple ingredients from the same category, it is counted multiple times for that category. The actual number of instances per ingredient does not influence this count. Although the total number of ingredient classes was significantly reduced during the relabeling process, the number of images per category remained relatively consistent, with a mean difference of 64 and a standard deviation of 56.1. Because images can contain multiple ingredients from the same category, we define the image count for a category as the total number of images that include at least one ingredient belonging to it. This approach ensures that the effects of label merging are properly reflected in the statistical analysis.

Fig. 1. Number of ingredient classes per food category.

Fig. 2. Image-wise distribution of categories before and after the relabeling process.

3.4 Annotation analysis

For evaluation purposes, the 3,977 images in our dataset were split into training and test sets using a 76:24 ratio, resulting in 3,024 training images and 953 test images. This split was generated using a weighted sampling algorithm that prioritized ingredients with fewer examples, ensuring that both subsets contained at least one instance of each ingredient class and maintained a similar instance distribution. Since less frequent ingredients often appear alongside more common ones, this method helped balance the class representation across the split.

Regarding image resolution, the dataset contains images ranging from 1280×720 pixels up to 4608×3456 pixels, with a median resolution of approximately 4032×2268 pixels, as shown in Figure 3. While the 4608×3456 images have the largest area, the maximum width and height across all images are 5664 pixels and 4032 pixels, respectively. These larger-dimension images often exhibit a 1:2 aspect ratio, differing from the more

common 4:3 and 16:9 (or 3:4 and 9:16 in portrait mode) formats. Figure 3 shows the distribution of image aspect ratios across the dataset.

Fig. 3. Analysis of image size: (a) shows the distribution of image resolutions, while (b) depicts the aspect ratio distribution.

The distribution of ingredients across images complicates efforts to maintain a strict instance-to-image ratio during dataset splitting. Ingredients are not uniformly distributed, and an image can contain multiple ingredient classes and multiple instances of each class. As shown in Figure 4 (in comparison with Fig. 1), some categories have many instances but few ingredient classes. For instance, the Eggs and Dairy category contains only 11 ingredient classes, yet has the highest number of instances, appearing in over 40% of the dataset. In contrast, the Spices, Flavourings, Sauces & Cooking/Baking Aids category has more than triple the number of classes, but appears in just over 30% of the images.

Some ingredients also tend to appear with multiple instances per image, depending on how they are stored. For example, eggs are often stored in cartons, and each visible egg is individually annotated. In contrast, larger items such as milk cartons or bottles usually appear only once or twice per image. The left side of Fig. 5a highlights this contrast by showing the ingredients that appear in the most images and those with the highest total number of instances. On the other end of the spectrum, rare ingredients such as capers, part of the Spices, Flavourings, Sauces & Cooking/Baking Aids category, are typically annotated only once per image and appear alongside other ingredients. Their limited presence is illustrated in Fig. 5b.

Fig. 4. Comparison between the number of images in which an ingredient from a category is present and their total number of instances.

Fig. 5. Number of images in which each ingredient appears. The plots show the top 30 ingredients that appear in the largest (left) and smallest (right) number of images. The blue bars represent the training set and orange bars represent the test set. The number at the end of each bar indicates the total number of images in which the ingredient appears.

In terms of instance distribution per image, most images contain up to four instances, with an average of two to three (see Fig. 6). To better assess the diversity of ingredients per image, we computed a histogram of the number of unique ingredient classes per image. As shown in Fig. 7, approximately 90% of images contain up to three unique ingredients, with the majority having just two. Figure 9 presents the aspect ratio distribution for images in the train and test sets, with aspect ratios capped at 5.0 for legibility. Notably, 38 bounding boxes in the training set and 12 in the test set exceed this aspect ratio.

Bounding box sizes range from 47×47 pixels up to 4607×2592 pixels. Large bounding boxes are often due to object orientation or rotation, as illustrated in Fig. 8. Figure 10 shows the distribution of bounding box sizes for both train and test sets, with mean bounding box sizes of approximately 1010×950 pixels (train) and 990×931 pixels (test). These values were obtained by applying K-Means clustering to the bounding box dimensions.

Fig. 6. Histogram showing the number of instances per image. For improved readability, all images containing more than 10 instances are grouped into a single bin. The maximum number of instances in a single image is 30.

Fig. 7. Histogram showing the number of unique ingredient classes per image. Similar to Fig. 8, images containing more than 10 unique ingredients are grouped into a single bin. The maximum number of unique ingredients in a single image is 16.

Fig. 8. Example of an image where the bounding box for an object ('Bread') is as large as the image itself because the annotated object extends out-of-view and the ground-truth mask touches the edges of the image.

Fig. 9. Distribution of number bounding boxes per aspect ratio (ratio of width over height). The train and test distributions are not stacked, but superimposed.

4. Benchmark Evaluation

4.1 Evaluation Models

We evaluated several deep learning models on the task of instance segmentation. This section provides a brief overview of the model architectures used in the evaluation. These architectures were selected based on their popularity and strong performance in related tasks. Most of the models are capable of producing instance segmentation masks directly or can serve as backbones for downstream applications, such as estimating the volume or weight of ingredients. Additionally, these models can be integrated into multi-task systems, where segmentation is combined with other predictions, or embedded into neural-based recommender systems that incorporate user profiles, consumption history, and ingredient images as input.

Fig. 10. Distribution of the bounding box sizes. The bounding box sizes from the train and test sets are plotted one over the other.

We evaluated several deep neural network architectures for instance segmentation on our dataset. Mask R-CNN [16] is a two-stage architecture that performs segmentation on candidate regions of interest. Hybrid Task Cascade (HTC) [17] extends Cascade R-CNN [18] by interleaving mask branches and incorporating a global segmentation head, enhancing foreground-background separation. RTMDet [19] is a real-time, single-stage detector that uses large-kernel convolutions and a dynamic soft label assigner. It supports instance segmentation with minimal architectural changes. Mask2Former [20] introduces masked attention in the transformer decoder to improve convergence and performance for panoptic, instance, and semantic segmentation. InternImage [21] is a scalable CNN backbone inspired by Vision Transformers (ViT) [22] that uses deformable convolutions to capture long range patterns in the image.

Table 2. Experimental results for the benchmark evaluation of the selected instance segmentation models. We use AP^b (for bounding-boxes) and AP^m (for segmentation) to represent the AP metric for each task. #params denotes the number of trainable parameters for each model.

Model	#params	AP^b	AP_{50}^b	AP^m	AP_{50}^m
<i>Mask R-CNN</i> <i>ResNet-50</i> [16]	45M	46.5	61.1	51	60.6
<i>HTC</i> <i>ResNet-50</i> [17]	78M	52.8	61	54.1	60.3
<i>RTMDet-L</i> [19]	57M	63.7	70.2	55.6	59.5
<i>Mask2Former</i> <i>ResNet-50</i> [20]	44M	58.9	64.5	63.6	68.2
<i>Mask R-CNN</i> <i>InternImage-S</i> [21]	69M	64	75.2	67.8	75.2
<i>Cascade Mask R-CNN</i> <i>InternImage-L</i> [21]	277M	76.2	81	76.6	81

4.2 Experimental Results

The experiments were conducted using MMDetection [23], an object detection and instance segmentation framework featuring a comprehensive model zoo. All models were evaluated using the COCO metrics for instance segmentation.

We used SGD as the optimizer for the first two models in Table 2, and AdamW [24] for the remaining ones, following the original authors recommended hyperparameters. Cosine Annealing [25] with a warm-up of 4000 iterations was used for learning rate

scheduling. All models were trained for 120 epochs (approximately 480k iterations) on two NVIDIA V100 GPUs (32 GB each), with evaluation performed every 10 epochs. Table 2 reports results from the best-performing checkpoint for each model.

We enhanced the training using image augmentation techniques. For data augmentation, we applied chromatic distortion, image compression, blur, and ISO noise, along with horizontal flips and random resizing (between 640 and 800 pixels on the long edge while maintaining aspect ratio). All models followed this pipeline, except for RTMDet, which used its default augmentations.

As shown in Table 2, the best performance was achieved by the largest model we tested—Cascade Mask R-CNN with InternImage-L (277M parameters)—both in terms of mean average precision (mAP) for instance segmentation and bounding box detection. Some qualitative results from this model can be seen in Fig. 11.

These results align with expectations, as segmentation tasks typically benefit from models with larger capacity. However, several challenges remain. As illustrated in Figure 12, some classes appear in only a few images or contain few instances, resulting in underwhelming performance. We attribute this to the long-tailed class distribution of our dataset—a common issue also observed in real-world household ingredient distributions.

Fig. 11. Qualitative results for *Cascade Mask R-CNN InternImage-L*. (a), (d), and (g) represent the original images, (b), (e), and (h) are the images with ground truth annotations, and (c), (f), and (i) show the predictions.

Fig. 12. The worst scoring ingredient classes when evaluating using *Cascade Mask R-CNN InternImage-L* using the AP metric, sorted decreasingly by mask segmentation AP. For every class we have also displayed in parenthesis the number of instances in the train and test set, respectively.

5. Limitations

One limitation of our proposed dataset is the inherent class imbalance across its 166 categories, given that it contains less than 4000 images. This is a common challenge in real-world data collection, where some food ingredients are naturally more prevalent than others. In our dataset, this manifests as a long-tail distribution where a few classes are very well-represented, while many others are not. For instance, less common ingredients such as “capers” are present in as few as four images, making it challenging for a model to learn their distinct features robustly. This imbalance could lead to a performance bias, where models trained on this data achieve high accuracy on common ingredients but struggle to reliably detect the rarer ones. To address this limitation, we have employed a class-balancing strategy through resampling, where images containing rarer classes were given a higher probability of being selected. While this approach helps mitigate the risk of creating a model biased towards common ingredients, the underlying imbalance in the dataset itself remains.

Furthermore, the dataset's real-world nature also introduces other potential biases. First, there is a strong co-occurrence bias, where certain ingredients are more likely to appear together, potentially leading a model to rely on contextual cues rather than the intrinsic features of the ingredients themselves. Second, there is a significant variance in the number of instances per image. Some classes, like “eggs”, have a high instance count per image, whereas larger items might appear as a single instance per image. As such, the difference between instance frequency and image frequency can complicate the training process.

6. Conclusions

We have developed large datasets of food ingredients annotated with instance segmentation masks. The dataset includes 166 ingredient classes and a total of 11,904 segmented instances. Images were collected from real-world environments, such as refrigerator shelves, tabletops, and pantries, and exhibit a wide variety of lighting conditions, resolutions, viewing angles, and image quality.

To validate the usefulness of the dataset, we conducted a series of experiments using different instance segmentation models. We provided details on the experimental setup, including hyperparameter configurations and the image augmentation techniques applied during training. The benchmark results indicate that challenges such as the long-tailed distribution of classes, where some ingredients appear far more frequently than others, remain a limiting factor in achieving consistently high performance.

As part of future work, we plan to explore strategies for addressing this class imbalance, including loss function reweighting and data resampling. Additionally, we aim to implement an active learning framework to extend the dataset efficiently. This will support the inclusion of new ingredient classes and improve model performance, particularly for underrepresented categories. Our *IntAli* dataset is available upon request.

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